

Application of open-source CFD code SU² to Ascent configuration of Reusable Launch Vehicle

Amit Sachdeva*, Pankaj Priyadarshi
Aerodynamic Design and Data Synthesis Division
Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Thiruvanthapuram, India.
(amit_sachdeva@vssc.gov.in , aero_amit@hotmail.com)

Abstract

First demonstration flight of RLV-TD vehicle successfully took place in May 2016. Vehicle Aerodynamics played a major role in design and development of this mission. Extensive amount of tests and numerical simulations have been carried for aerodynamic characterization of the vehicle. In the present work, CFD simulations have been carried out over ascent configuration of RLV-TD vehicle at typical transonic Mach numbers and angles of attack. An open-source CFD code SU² has been explored and used to carry out the simulations. Results from CFD simulations are compared with the test data for generating confidence in clearance of the flight hardware.

Key words: RLV-TD, CFD, SU²

Nomenclature

M	Mach number	C_{PM}	Pitching moment coefficient
α	Angle of attack	C_p	Pressure coefficient
C_A	Axial force coefficient	SU ²	Stanford University Unstructured
C_N	Normal force coefficient	SA	Spalart Allamaras Turbulence model
X_{CP}	Center of pressure	SST	Shear Stress Transport Turbulence model

Introduction

ISRO has successfully demonstrated the flight of Reusable Launch Vehicle- Technology Demonstrator (RLV-TD) in May 2016. This launch demonstrated many key technologies like hypersonic aero-thermodynamic design, autonomous navigation guidance and control etc. Aerodynamics played a major role in design and development of the overall mission. The first stage is a solid rocket booster, which took the winged body configuration to an altitude of 70 km and peak Mach number around 5 and then RLV-TD separated from the booster and reentered into the atmosphere.

It is a complex and challenging configuration from aerodynamics point of view. To design and assess the aerodynamic behavior of ascent/decent flight, large number of wind tunnel tests and numerical simulations have been carried out. Conditions at transonic Mach numbers are critical from structural design point of view. For ascent configuration, booster fins play a major role to control the vehicle. Allowable fin deflection for controllability of the vehicle is limited by the structural design margins. To assess these margins, several wind tunnel tests were carried out for ascent configuration with fin and without fin. To generate the load distribution over fins, wings etc., CFD simulations have been carried out. An open-source CFD code Stanford University Unstructured (SU²) [1, 2] has been used for carrying out these simulations and results are compared with the test data.

Stanford University Unstructured (SU²) CFD code

SU² is an open-source Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) code. It is primarily tailored for solving compressible flow Navier-Stokes equations. This code has originated from Aerospace Engineering Department of the Stanford University and is under active development worldwide. It

is Finite Volume based unstructured grid solver, which can resolve flow to the wall. It has SA and SST turbulence model [3, 4], explicit and implicit time marching schemes and various boundary conditions to deal with variety of problems. It also has adjoint based solver for aerodynamic shape optimization. This code has got good scalability on the distributed cluster. Many papers have been published in past few years, which presents various features, validations as well as capabilities of the code. SU² is written in C++ using Object Oriented Programming concept, which allows good flexibility of adding new capabilities and reusing the existing capabilities. Code can be downloaded from its website. Also development of the code is maintained on GitHub.

Code to code verification

SU² Code has been validated thoroughly by the developers for various test cases. We have also validated it for few relevant problems. In first test case, axisymmetric simulation have been carried out over ogive PLF configuration at transonic Mach number (M=0.95) using SU² and commercial code CFD++. SST k- ω turbulence model has been used for carrying out the simulations. Figure 1a compares the pressure palettes and the surface pressure distribution for the two codes. Flow features (shock, expansion etc.) captured by the two codes are nearly identical. This reflects in comparison Cp distribution plot as well.

Figure-1a Comparison of axisymmetric simulation over ogive payload fairing

Figure-1b Comparison of Mach contours in yaw plane over a launch vehicle configuration with ogive Heat Shield

Another validation exercise of 3D simulation over launch vehicle configuration was carried out at Mach number 1.2. Figure 1b presents comparison of Mach number contours from the two codes. Code captures various features like shock expansions etc. crisply and results compares well with the commercial code CFD++. In this case, aerodynamic coefficients matched within 2% and Xcp matched within 0.2 m between the two codes.

This validation exercise gave confidence of using the open-source CFD code SU² for other relevant practical applications.

Results and Discussion

a) Grid generation

An unstructured mesh with more than 30 prism layers have been generated using commercial software Pointwise [5]. First cell size has been kept sufficiently small to ensure $y^+ \sim 1$. RANS simulations have been carried out with SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model. MUSCL reconstruction with Venkatakrishnan limiter has been used for second order accurate solution and HLLC scheme [6] has been used for convective flux discretization. Implicit time stepping has been used for all the simulations. Simulations have been carried out at Mach number 0.85 and 0.93 (critical from structural load point of view) at various angles of attack.

Figure 2 presents unstructured grid over surface as well as cut section for winged body as well as booster part.

Figure-2 surface mesh and volume mesh at mid face cut section

b) Convergence monitoring -

Forces and moments have been monitored for all the simulations to arrive at the converged solution. For most of the cases, first order accurate simulation has been carried out for few thousand iterations followed by the second order accurate simulation. Figure 3 shows convergence plots for Axial and normal force coefficients for Mach number 0.93, angle of attack -3 deg case. Simulations have been run for sufficient number of iterations to ensure the iterative convergence of various coefficients.

Figure-3 Convergence plot for Axial and normal force coefficients ($M=0.93$, $\alpha=-3$ deg)

c) Results

Simulations have been carried out for Mach numbers 0.85 and 0.93 at angles of attack $\pm 3^\circ$ and 5° . Figure-4 presents Mach number palette in pitch and yaw plane for Mach number 0.93, angle of attack -3° case. It can be observed that various flow features are captured crisply. Figure 5 presents pressure palette over the body of the vehicle displaying high and low pressure zones over it. Open-source software ParaView [7] has been used for the post-processing.

Figure-4 Mach number palette in pitch and yaw plane ($M=0.93$, $\alpha=-3$ deg)

Figure-5 C_p palette over the body of the RLV ascent configuration

Figure-5 Variation of C_N and C_{PM} with angle of attack

calculate the effect of fins (augmentation of loads due to fin), tests were carried out for configurations with fin as well as without fins. CFD simulations have been carried out for both configurations at wind tunnel test conditions. The main aim of the CFD simulations was to generate load distribution over the fins of the booster, which was not available from the wind tunnel tests. With the good match, load distribution could be confidently generated and supplied to the structure team for further analysis.

Figure-6 shows comparison of simulation results (normal force and pitching moment coefficients) with test data for Mach number 0.85 and 0.93. Simulation results are in good agreement with the test data. Load augmentation due to fin matches within 7% in C_N and 5% in C_{PM} for $\alpha = \pm 3$ deg while for 5 deg case these are on slightly higher side (within 16%). Overall good comparison is obtained between test data and CFD results.

Conclusion

Open-source CFD code SU² has been used for carrying out CFD simulation over RLV-TD ascent configuration at transonic Mach numbers. Results from numerical simulations compare well with the wind tunnel data. Code has been also validated against commercial CFD code for couple of test cases for typical launch vehicle configurations at transonic Mach numbers. This work gave good confidence to use CFD based load distribution for structural design and analysis.

Importantly, this study also demonstrated the practical usage of open-source CFD code for the launch vehicle problems as well as gave confidence of using the open-source CFD code SU² for further applications to the complex launch vehicle problems.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to acknowledge Shri K Manokaran for providing the mesh for the RLV ascent configuration and Shri C Babu for helping in one of the validation exercise. They would also like to thank Shri Vinod Kumar for his suggestions as well as Shri Priyankar Bandopadhyay for his suggestions and feedbacks. I would also like to thank EAD team in VSSC for providing wind tunnel test data for the comparison.

References

- [1] Palacios F, Colonno M, Aranake A, Campos A, Copeland S, Economon T, Lonkar A, Lukaczyk T, Taylor T and Alonso J, “Stanford University Unstructured (SU²): An open-source integrated computational environment for multi-physics simulation and design”, 51 st AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting, 2013, AIAA 2013-0287
- [2] Palacios, F., Economon, T., Aranake, A., Copeland, S., Lonkar, A., Lukaczyk, T., Manosalvas, D., Naik, K., Santi- ago Padr´ on, A., Tracey, B., Variyar, A., and Alonso, J., “Stanford university unstructured (SU²): Open-source analysis and design technology for turbulent flows,” AIAA 52nd Aerospace Sciences Meeting, SciTech, 13-17 January, National Harbor, MD, 2014
- [3] Spalart P and Allmaras S, “A One-Equation Turbulence Model for Aerodynamic Flows”, AIAA 92-0439
- [4] Menter F, “Zonal Two Equation k- ω Turbulence Models for Aerodynamic Flows.”, AIAA 93-2906
- [5] Pointwise V17 user manual, 2016
- [6] Toro E. F., Spruce M, Speares W., Restoration of the contact surface in the HLL Riemann solver, Shock Waves, 1994
- [7] The ParaView Guide, Version – 5.0, 17 June, 2016
- [8] Blazek J, “Computational Fluid Dynamics: Principles and Applications”, Elsevier, 2001